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Paul's Counsel in 1 Corinthians 7:1 & 8, Preferment of Celibacy: Its Authenticity and Effects among the Catholic Priests

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Abstract

Celibacy simply means not married and not having sex, from a specific time till the rest of your life, especially because of your religious belief. It is a very strong and widely held mandate of service in the Catholic Church. There is no doubt that the Catholic Church and other individuals that uphold celibacy or virginity dwell heavily on 1 Corinthians 7:1 & 8 as their biblical evidence for the doctrine. It is also certain that Paul's counsels on relationships particularly in 1 Corinthians 7 have given rise to serious marital concerns. Many scholars have written so much on 1 Corinthians 7, celibacy, and sexual sins. But more needs to be said about the original intention of Paul in 1 Corinthians 7:1 and 8 and its effects on our society today. And again, the authenticity of the rising number of people that claim to be practising celibacy is doubtful to many people. Can many people be faithful to such a sensitive doctrine? The theoretical frame work of Historical and theological methods is used to retrieve information from various sources. Library was used as a major source of information. Practice of celibacy that distinguished Catholic Church from other Christian Ministries or denominations was identified. The background of Paul was examined. Importance of marital counsel was discussed. The exegesis of 1 Corinthians 7:1 & 8 has been presented. Celibacy and virginity were clearly defined. Advantages and disadvantages of celibacy or virginity were listed. The likely reasons Paul preferred celibacy were suggested. The effects of Paul's counsel on the preferment of celibacy has been stated. And finally, practical and biblical recommendations for the Church and the society were highlighted.

Keywords: Catholic, Celibacy, Counsel, Marriage, Paul, Virginity

Introduction

Catholic priest is without a wife. Indeed, this image has been built-up by the church administration as an essential part of its own *esprit de corps* (Thomas O'Loughlin. 2013). It is now a popular practice for some individuals in our society to abscond marriage for various reasons especially among the Catholic priests. What is the relevance of celibacy in the Church? If the first fourteen Popes were married men, and the priests in our contemporary society are been denied of same privilege, then we need to go back to the Church history to remind one another the original tradition (Kasomo Daniel. 2012). Most times, it sounds very strange to discover that some highly religious sets of people have chosen not to marry or engage in any form of sexual activities for the sake of the gospel. Some people believe that it is possible for very few people to be faithful till the end. Some believe that it is not possible for any healthy person, especially men to stay without having sex for a long period of time except such individuals are having some health challenges or if they have castrated themselves like Origen (Elizabeth Abbott. 2000). It is also

alleged that celibacy as recommended by Apostle Paul contradicts the institution of marriage and can be very misleading because God cannot contradict himself. God said in Genesis 2:18 that, "It is not good for the man to be alone. I will make a helper suitable for him" (NIV). It is therefore necessary to find out the background of Paul very well and verify his state of health and physical fitness as of the time he was counselling the Corinthians on male and female relationship. How practicable is this celibacy? What challenges are those that vowed to stay away from sex are facing? And what are the effects of this strong doctrine in our society, especially in Catholic Church? The purpose of this paper is not to run down the importance of this principal doctrine, rather; it intends to re-examine the validity of celibacy and its significance in the Church.

Importance of Marital Counsel in the Contemporary Society

As we listen to news daily and witness the events within our vicinities, it is no longer news that marriages contracted in the church, court, or traditionally are collapsing every day. For various reasons, some couples will just conclude that they can no longer continue as husband and wives. Marriage, as a social institution, has been around for thousands of years. It is easy to assume that such an institution can only change slowly. But development since the middle of the 20th century show that this assumption is wrong. In many countries marriages are becoming less common, people are marrying later, unmarried people are increasingly living together and, in many countries, we are seeing a lots of divorces and serious conflicts. Within the last two decades the institution of marriage has changed more than in thousands of years before (Esteban Ortiz-Ospina and Max Rose. 2020).

Again, Paul specifies some qualities of bishops and priests: they should have shown skill in running their own families and be monogamous (1 Tim 3:2 and 3:12; and Tit 1:6); and indeed, there is a general caution against those who prohibit marriage on religious grounds (1 Tim 4:3). Yet, by the fourth century something had changed. Then we see the first signs of concern about the compatibility of marriage and priesthood. For example, at a local synod in Spain (c. 306) it was decreed that any cleric who would not undertake absolute continence should be deposed (Thomas O'Loughlin. 2013). Therefore, there is a desperate need for marital counselling if we want to get the best of human relationship in our society. So, the importance of marital counsel cannot be over-emphasised.

Celibacy and Virginty Defined

Celibacy simply means not married and not having sex, from a specific time till the rest of your life, especially because of your religious belief. For instance, Catholic priests are required to be celibate (Longman Advanced Dictionary of Contemporary English. (6th edition) 2014). Celibacy is here understood as the unmarried state chosen in the light of the Christian faith and in particular as one of the duties of the state in life of the clergy of the Latin Church by which they are forbidden to marry and obliged to live in total continence (Karl Rahner. 1975). Virginty is the condition of never having had sex. Both celibacy and virginty signify chastity, maidenhood, virtue, honour, purity, pureness, innocence, decency, modesty, dignity, and self-denial. Celibacy originated in the early church as an ascetic discipline, noted partly in a Neo-Platonic contempt for the physical world that had nothing to do with the Gospel (Daniel Kasomo. 2012). The

rejection of sexual enjoyment by men fit nicely with a patriarchal belittling of women. Non virginal women, typified by Eve as the temptress of Adam, were seen as a source of sin. According to Matthew 19:3-12 Jesus campaigns for discretionary celibacy. For nearly 2000 years the Catholic Church has decreed Church laws and doctrines planned to more clearly explain the teachings of Christ. But curiously, while history discloses that Jesus carefully chosen only married men to serve as His apostles, the Church today prohibits priestly marriage. Also, today the Catholic Church is among Christian denominations experiencing worldwide condemnation from "scandalous" allegations of sex abuse committed against women and children by priests and bishops. Historically, scandals similar to these are known to have appeared only after mandatory celibacy laws were first instituted, centuries after Christ. Why were these changes made? (Daniel Kasomo. 2012).

Paul's Counsel and the Exegesis of 1 Corinthians 7:1 and 8

1 Corinthians 7:1 - Now for the matters you wrote about: It is good for a man not to marry. **Περὶ δὲ ὧν ἐγραψατέ μοι, καλὸν ἀνθρώπῳ γυναῖκος μὴ ἄπτεσθαι.** The above is 1 Corinthians 7:1 Meaning: Now for the matters you wrote about: It is good for a man not to marry (NIV). "Now for the matter you wrote about ..." It is adequately apparent that the primary part of this epistle was written in answer to some enquiries which had been sent to the apostle in a letter from the Corinthian church; and the first question seems to be this: "Is it appropriate for a man to marry in the present state of affairs of the church? The question concerning the expediency or in expediency of marriage was often debated among the early philosophers; and many, though inclined to decide against it, because of the difficulties and attentions connected with it, tolerated it in their opinions; because, though an evil, it was judged to be a necessary evil. The words of Menander are full to this effect: "If a man consider marriage in a proper point of view, it is an evil; but then it is a necessary evil." (Matthew Henry's Commentary on the whole Bible *in six volumes, carefully revised and corrected* - 1706-1721). God demonstrated His interest in and the value placed on the marriage and family, by being practically involved in its institution. He carefully put it together step by step. He put man into sleep, made a woman and presented her to man. Therefore, giving the impression that marriage is divine (Faith Oyedepo. 2019). God's view about marriage is that it is good and it is to be enjoyed. God's view is contrary to man's view on marriage. Some people say, "Marriage is a necessary evil." Others introduce a state of irony into this holy institution. They contend that the married are looking for a way of escape, while the unmarried are eager to get into it. This assertion is borne out of man's philosophy and the experience of those who have not found fulfilment in marriage. But neither philosophy nor experience is the truth; God's Word is. Buttressing the fact that marriage is good, Paul says: Marriage is honourable in all... (Hebrews 13:4). If marriage is evil, it cannot at the same time be honourable. Since it is honourable, it cannot be evil. James also says that: Every good gift and every perfect gift is from above, and cometh down from the Father of lights, with whom is no variableness, neither shadow of turning (James 1:17). Scripturally, marriage is good! It is the use to which some put it that paints a deceptive picture of evil.

1 Corinthians 7:8 λεγω δε τοις ἀγαμοις και χηραις, καλον αὐτοις ἐαν μεινωσιν ὡς καγω meaning “Now to the unmarried and the widows I say: It is good for them to stay unmarried, as I am” - NIV

The expression also may carry in it an intimation that Christians must avoid all occasions of this sin, and flee all fleshly lusts, and incentives to them; must neither look on nor touch a woman, so as to provoke lustful inclinations. I say therefore to the unmarried and widows, it is good for them if they abide even as I. The unmarried and widows - It is supposed that the apostle speaks here of men who had been married, in the word ἀγαμοι, but were now widowers; as he does of women who had been married, in the word χήραι, but were now widows. And when he says ὡς καγω, even as I, he means that he himself was a widower; for several of the ancients rank Paul among the married apostles. This indicates that Paul married but later lost his wife. He chose not to remarry and claimed that it is better for him to concentrate on the preaching of the gospel instead of bordering himself with the burden of marriage.

History of Celibacy

Celibacy can also be traced to Paganism. Among the ancient Greece, premarital chastity was such an essential requirement in brides before they were thrust into marriage. Three ambitious goddesses maintain a lifelong vigilance over the virginity of their children (Abbott Elizabeth. 2000). Origen, the great Christian thinker well-known for castrating himself to make himself a eunuch for the Kingdom of Heaven, as well as for his fascinating teaching and deep writing in Scripture, philosophy, and ethics, had first expressed this idea. Origen maintained that you cannot be holy without punishing the flesh in every ramification. Self-denial and separation from the outside world with its sinful distractions is the only way to true Christianity (Abbott Elizabeth. 2000).

The biblical foundations of celibacy are taken to be the saying of the Lord about not marrying (becoming a eunuch) for the sake of the kingdom of heaven as stated in Matthew 19:10. The disciples suggested celibacy because they did not wish to give up the liberty of divorce. Luke 18:29 also suggests celibacy for the sake of the reign of God. Mark 10:29 talks about leaving one's wife for the sake of Jesus and the gospel. Matthew 22:30 and Mark 12:25 affirm that in the resurrection there will be no marriage. Paul also wished all men to be in the same state as himself as mentioned in 1 Corinthians 7:7. The unmarried is committed to the things of the Lord, while the attention of the married is divided – 1 Corinthians 7:32. The above texts do not link celibacy directly to the priestly ministry.

Celibacy as an obligation of the priestly state was introduced only progressively. It originated from great significance attached to virginity as in Matthew 25:1-13; 2 Corinthians 11:2; Ephesians 5:25-30, 21; 2 & 9. Celibacy also grew from the way of life of ascetics and monks with their recourse to the Old Testament laws of purity. The advancement of the law of celibacy was significantly promoted by the precept laid down in the Pastoral letters that bishops, priests and deacons should be “husband of only one wife” (1 Timothy 3:2, 12; Titus 1:6ff), though the precise meaning of the principle was debated (Karl Rahner. 1975). Rules dealing with celibacy are set up as early as the beginning of the 4th century. It was inspired by the desire for total dedication and also to some extent under the influence of dualistic Gnostic tendencies of a Manichaean

type. Many priests felt bound to discontinue marriage relationships after their ordination. In the Eastern Churches celibacy triumphed only for those who were well appointed with the fullness of the priesthood, the bishops, and was given force of law in the 7th century by the Emperor Justinian and the second Trullan Synod (Karl Rahner. 1975).

However, in the West the declarations of the Synod of Elvira were widely imposed by Pope Siricius (DS 118f. 185). An effort to prescribe celibacy as a universal Church law was made at the First Council of Nicaea (325), but did not meet with success. Leo 1 and Gregory 1 extended the law to include sub deacons. Since what was forbidden was not so much marriage as the continuation of married life. Promises of discontinuation of married life were often demanded of candidates for the priesthood (and their wives) between the 5th and 7th centuries (Ruth. A. Tucker. 1987). For over 700 years after Constantine, Roman Emperors and later European royals controlled papal elections and personally appointed bishops and abbots who served at their discretion, not the Pope's. Monasteries and dioceses brought great wealth to these secular lords through Simony, although little accrued to Rome. During all that time bishops and priests were married and Churches became Sacramental filling stations owned by mercenary clerics who willed them to family heirs, who then often bought and sold these valuable offices. The Church had a strong need to curb priestly heirs' power and corruption, and this problem was solved when Popes submitted to the Emperor's secular authority, with agreement that Cardinals alone would elect future popes. Finally, after a 700-year struggle, and desiring to eliminate future loss of wealth and control over married clerics, mandatory celibacy laws preventing future heirs were finally instituted.

Separation of spouses was also demanded. It is as clear as a bell as from the 6th century a major factor that led to the promotion of celibacy in the Middle Ages was the efforts to prevent the alienation of Church properties, which might otherwise pass into the possession of the priests' family. This gave rise in the 12th century to the marriage of those in major orders. Despite the sharp controversy at the time of the Reformation, the Council of Trent re-affirmed the principle that clerics in major orders were incapable of contracting matrimony (DS 1809). In the form already laid down by the Council of Nicaea "by virtue of ancient tradition" that there should be no marriage after the reception of a major order, the magisterium held fast to this law, as if it were apostolic regulation, even in Vatican 11 and the documents which have appeared since then (Karl Rahner. 1975).

According to the law in force in the Latin Church, as laid down by the CIC, (In 1983 Code of Canon Law (abbreviated 1983 CIC from its Latin title *Codex Iuris Canonici*), also called the *Johanno-Pauline Code*. Is the "fundamental body of ecclesiastical laws for the Latin Church." So, the Catholic Integrated Community (CIC) is an apostolic community within the Roman Catholic according to Decree *Apostolicam actuositatem* No. 18/19 of the Second Vatican Council). clerics in minor orders lose their clerical status by contracting matrimony (can. 132, 2). Clerics in major orders are forbidden to marry. They are obliged in a special way to preserve chastity. A sin against chastity is a sacrilege (can. 132, § 1). And if it involves an external breach of the law (can. 2195) incurs sanctions (can. 2325). All attempt to contract matrimony are null and void (can. 1072) and to presume to enter upon a civil form of irregularity (can. 985, § 3), loss of ecclesiastical office (can. 188, 5) and excommunication (Karl Rahner. 1975). It has also been noted that ...there is a

mistrust among twentieth century Christians that the female holy ones were not quite as equal as their brothers ... Wives of members of the clergy are rarely mentioned in a treatment of medieval Church minister, except in regulation to keep them separated from their husbands. That is because as a rule, those who committed themselves to "professional" Church ministry during the Middle Ages also committed themselves to celibacy (Eleamor McLanghlin 1979).

Celibacy stems also originated from a competition to be as holy as the pagan priesthood? For instance, Athenagoras advocated that the very thought of sexual pleasure was evil. "Among us are many men and women who have grown to old age without marrying, in the hope of being closer to God." (Sipe, Richard. 1995). Justin Martyr disagreed with all matrimonial sexuality apart from "reproductive intentionality" and identified with pride to some Christians who rejected marriage and survived in perfect continence. Tatian founded the Encratites, who forbidden sexual intercourse, intoxicants, and meat. He proclaimed that woman is entirely a creation of the devil, but man is only halfway so (below the waist). He first claimed that Jesus was a celibate. Tertullian did not denounce sexual intercourse but he questioned why God had conceived the sordid act! Origen thought that celibacy was more appropriate of Christians, and acknowledged notions that were more pagan than Christian. He contended that since pagans refrained from sexual intercourse in order to worship idols, how much more should worshipers of the supreme God abstain (Hoge, Dean and Jaqueline Wenger. 2003).

However, Clement of Alexandria, Origen's teacher, was bothered by Christians who did not identify that a couple collaborates in the holy work of creation. He regarded celibacy as a timid avoidance of responsibility. "Is it not possible to live in harmony with God? Is it not permitted also for both the married person and his partner to care for things of the Lord?" he asked.

By the time the Council of Elvira in Spain (Hoge, Dean and Jaqueline Wenger. 2003)

Other Possible Reasons for Paul's Counsel in 1Corinthians 7:1 & 8

Paul's physical characteristics as listed below could be part of the reasons for his preferment of celibacy: Paul is Short, Bald (ing), Black beard – Jews despised the Roman habit of shaving (http://www.amazon.com/gp/product/B0000DHFZT/ref=olp_product_details). He was exuded an aura of confidence (arrogance?) and had bow-legged. He has some kind of physical ailment – "Thorn in the flesh" (2 Corinthians 12:7), both painful and humiliating (Galatians 4:13-15). He probably had malaria, back problems, and epilepsy (see: Galatians 4:14, scorn = "spit out") Men would spit in the presence of an epileptic in a fit to keep themselves from taking on the evil (C. T. Wood, 1932). These physical ailments of Paul are more than enough for him to recommend celibacy. Paul was ready to carry his cross. Yoruba people of Nigeria will say: 'O gba kamu'

Advantages and Disadvantages of Celibacy

Some of the benefits of celibacy include the following: the fact that someone gives himself to God unconditionally. There is little or no concern for family and marital responsibilities. There is an amplified concentrated on goals. There is a fortification from the worries of relationship and sexuality. The tendency that a celibate will be closer to God is undisputable all other things being equal. Celibacy is one way of obeying Christ's invitation: (*Letter of Ignatius to Polycarp*, V, W. R. Shoedel, ed. Koester, *Ignatius of Antioch, A commentary on the Letters of St Ignatius of*

Antioch, Philadelphia 1985). Celibacy helps a lot to focus on other important areas of life without unnecessary distractions that usually arise as a result of sexual desire from the opposite sex. A celibate does not need to take any risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases. The celibates are unlikely to notice any negative physical side effects on their health. The detriments are also enumerated below: According to research, only ten percent of all priests and bishops effectively refrain from sex during their priesthood. Ninety percent participate in sex, 50 percent uninterruptedly and 40 percent occasionally. Of those, 30-50 percent are homosexually oriented and their sexual activity is comparable to heterosexual priests and bishops. Similar studies from Spain, Switzerland, South Africa, and the Philippines produced similar numbers. In areas of South America and Africa more than half of all priests have wives/mistresses. A major problem that goes unreported by the media is priestly sex abuse of women and young girls. Female abuse statistics are comparable to male pedophilia abuse. This is the sad state of our priesthood today (Rose, Michael S. 2002). Again, a 2016 study found that men who ejaculate at least 21 times per month had a lower risk of prostate cancer compare with those who ejaculate 4 – 7 times per month (Zawn Villines. October 11, 2023). When sexual abstinence is not voluntary, some individuals may feel negative effects on their mental health. Experts say months without physical touch can have adverse health impacts such as increased anxiety, depression and trouble sleeping. Lack of physical intimacy can also lead to touch starvation, which can contribute to loneliness, isolation and even compromise your immune system. Lack of sex may lead to sexual frustration (Paul Frysh. February 22, 2023). Sex is another way of exercising one's body, if one abstains from sex, the heart of the person may not work well.

Other Challenges of the Celibates

One of the challenges that arise is when members of consecrated life find in their environments, particularly during their ministry and pastoral undertakings, couples living in harmony in a good marital relation. They happen to unpleasantly deliberate on the priestly life they chose to live. It often happens when they encounter their old friends having settled married life. It causes a sort of regret and anguish regarding their own life. In many cases, people speak of danger in maintaining heterosexual friendships between consecrated people. It is a reality that many clergy and nuns 'entertain relations of husband-wife or lover-beloved under cover of an authentic friendship.' But it is a great problem growing drastically in our times. These examples show that many have not integrated their voluntary celibacy into religious existence. One of the important aspects regarding the diocesan priests must be emphasized. Such people experience a high level of loneliness and boredom. Unlike the religious communities, diocesans seem to be more vulnerable to sexual tendency. Also, they encounter a lot of people in their parish and ministry who are mostly married.

Authenticity of Celibacy and its Effects in the Society

Catholics are taught from childhood that Jesus' apostles ended sexual interaction with their wives in order to "Act in the person of Jesus", by adopting His celibate way of life and dedicating their lives to the spreading the Gospel unencumbered by family duties. But history discloses a different story (Kasomo Daniel. 2012). Jesus made few modifications in existing Jewish law for His

supporters. But among the most significant alterations He introduced were those in relation to marriage for Christians. Jewish men of the time were permitted to have more than one wife as well as concubines; Jesus outlawed polygamy. They were allowed to divorce; Jesus banned divorce (Matthew 19:9). And most essentially, Jewish law mandated all Jews, including priests, to marry by age 20 (Genesis 1:28), but Jesus certified Christians to stay unmarried if they freely chose to do so (Matthew 19:12). And, conflicting to current myth, Jesus did not necessitate His apostles to take a pledge of celibacy or to refrain from marital sex in order to duplicate His lifestyle; Christ permitted His apostles to liberally choose either marriage or celibacy. For these reasons the question of Jesus' celibacy is meaningless as defense for contemporary celibacy regulations that entered the Church centuries later. As Jesus left the Church, an individual's free choice to marry and multiply or to remain unmarried was permitted, and no constraint against future marriage by unmarried priests existed. Today many Catholic traditionalists have begun anew to scrutinize these teachings of Jesus and to compare them to the modern law of compulsory celibacy, a law that did not exist in the beginning (Charles A., Frazee. 1972).

Catholics seems to depend heavily on the extra Biblical records such as apocryphal than the New Testament letters. Catholics are not allowed to question Church teaching. Today, Church clarifications of compulsory celibacy pose unlimited problem because it is known by all that apostles and priests during the earliest era were married. In addition, in the New Testament St. Paul explicitly required bishops and deacons be married fathers, "capable of managing their families" (1Timothy 3). Even more detrimental to the notion of a required vow of celibacy, St. Paul precisely gave a sermon against newly converted Christian-Gnostics who brought with them a belief that all priests must reject cravings of the flesh in order to effectively intercede between God and man. This ascetic and dualistic belief of conflict between flesh and soul was first taught by Plato c.428BC and spread across the western world with Alexander the Great before 300BC. By Christ's time it had made its way into all religions' beliefs other than Orthodox Judaism and Christianity, who were unique among all beliefs (Kasomo Daniel. 2012).

An investigation of early modifications in Church teaching during the second and third centuries exposes comparable alterations in Jesus' original teachings also began to appear in some areas as Christianity rapidly spread throughout the Roman world. Many excellent scholars and philosophers from pagan religions became captivated with the resurrected Christ and converted, becoming prominent Christian teachers who thought priests should not desecrate themselves with sex. These converts are known as Patristic Fathers, and while they were noble and devout men, they also conveyed with them non-Christian philosophies that would forever affect the relationship of men and women, and marriage. Little did they understand that Christianity originally developed via House-churches, with priests reinforced by their wives as teachers (1Corinthians 16:19). Overcoming paganism and winning pagan converts were vital objectives for the developing Christian Church. This is where the story of compulsory celibacy actually originates. It is a story of change masked in the middle of a time before 350AD, when pseudo-Christian literatures were considered to be authentic source of Christian scripture, and popes were incontrovertible when claiming to talk ad hoc for Christ. For this reason, Christianity's first tradition of married priests was quite different from what the Church teaches today.

Gnostic endeavors to encourage the supremacy of celibacy and explain away the apostles' wives that St. Paul spoke of (1Corinthians 9-5), when he complained that he too should marry "just like the other apostles and Jesus' brothers", a myth was created, a myth that had no place in Christianity. This legend was first presented in apocryphal literatures suggesting the apostles had abandoned sex with their wives in order to imitate Jesus.

Practical and Biblical Recommendations

- i. In our contemporary society, many people find it difficult to appreciate the discipline of celibacy. We should be thankful to the clergy and the men and women who have made the total sacrifice of themselves out of love to serve our Lord and the Church (Fr. Saunders. 1996).
- ii. According to Matthew 19:3-12 Jesus campaigns for discretionary celibacy. Therefore, it is not expedient for any denomination to make it mandatory, rather, celibacy should have been optional and without any benefit attached to it.
- iii. Since history discloses that Jesus carefully chosen only married men to serve as His apostles, the Church today should not prohibit priestly marriage any longer.
- iv. There is no outstanding record to affirm that celibacy has reduced sexual sins among the priests rather it brings defilement into the priesthood instead of expected purity. Therefore, it is better to discourage priesthood celibacy.
- v. Sexual relationship is holy as long as it is expressed within the confinement of marriage. And again, holiness and purity go beyond illegal sexual relationship. Man is expected to demonstrate the fruit of the spirit through the power of the Holy Spirit after such a person must have accepted Jesus as His Lord and saviour before he can become holy. Therefore, celibacy is not and should not be the principal virtue for the priests. Love is the greatest as clearly stated in 1 Corinthians 13:13.
- vi. Though sex is regarded as immoral unless expressed in the matrimonial embrace of husband and wife, it is held as fundamentally healthy, a part of God's creation. To preserve itself, the Roman Catholic Church has to be much more careful not to let men with "deviations in their affections" enter the priesthood. Catholic should also re-affirm the Church's rule on celibacy, saying it should not be seen as a "useless" imposition but a vital part of a tradition in which the priest offers himself unconditionally to God.
- vii. Therefore, celibacy should not be imposed on anybody or recommended as a prerequisite for the clergy in any denomination. Though prophets like Elijah and Jeremiah have remained celibates throughout their life, these examples could not be considered as consecrated celibacy. Generally, singleness and bareness were considered as a matter of shame. The Jewish tradition gave much significance to family life. This is much evident in the Old Testament. Children were considered as favours of God Almighty. 'Sons are indeed a heritage from the lord, the fruit of the womb a reward' (Psalms 127:3). Since the survival of family and the tribe was among the main concerns of the Israelites, virginity was often considered as a misfortune even as a tragedy- and at times, as a curse and punishment. 'A boy or a girl who, for whatever reason, could not marry and have children

was pitied and even held in contempt. It was thought that they would never fulfill the reason of their existence, and that they failed in a basic debt they owed to all people.'

- viii. Celibacy is good for anyone that has the sufficient grace to cope with it, but it does not make the person holier than the married person as mentioned by the following reformers. Martin Luther the forerunner of reformation and protestant revolution in the church, at first didn't support married clergy. But later his views changed and in 1522, he rejected celibacy and married a nun. Calvin's opinions were more judicious. He advocated celibacy as an acceptable means of serving God but remarks that it is of no greater value than married life.

Conclusion

In the ecclesiological sense, just as Christ was totally united to the Church, the priest through his celibacy bonds his to the Church. He is better able to be a minister of the Word of God, listening to that Word, pondering its depth, living it and preaching it with whole-hearted conviction. He is the minister of the sacraments, and, especially through the Mass, acts in the person of Christ, offering himself totally to the Lord. Celibacy allows the priest greater freedom and flexibility in fulfilling his pastoral work: "(Celibacy) gives to the priest, even in the practical field, the maximum efficiency and the best disposition of mind, psychologically and affectively, for the continuous exercise of a perfect charity. This charity will permit him to spend wholly for the welfare of all, in a fuller and more concrete way" ("*Sacerdotalis Caelibatus*," No. 32). Finally, for anyone to live a celibacy life, it requires the grace of God. Repeatedly, celibacy is seen as a gift of the Holy Spirit. However, this gift is not just to keep one's physical desires under control or to live as a bachelor; this gift is being able to say "yes" to our Lord each day and live His life. Only Luke says that those who are celibate will be qualified for resurrection as recorded in Luke 20:27-37, a statement which is under serious scrutiny by the New Testament scholars. Matthew and Paul did not take it far, but they all agree that celibate is superior to marriage and family as in Matthew 19:3-12 and 1 Corinthians 7. What is important to this paper is that, you cannot really create a system of Christian sexual ethics that is "Biblical" because the Bible presents enthusiastically and fundamentally diverse opinions on the topic.

However, since there is no authentic record to show that God cannot use married priests to perform certain miracles which can only be performed by the celibates. We have numerous married priests in other denominations that are much focused, highly committed to God's work, and God has been using them to expand the scope of Christian faith over the years. If Pastor E.O. Adeboye of the Redeemed Christian Church of God is not a celibate, Bishop David Oyedepo of Living Faith Church is not a celibates and God has been using them for missions all over the world, then, what is special about being a celibate? What kind of achievement has any celibate made that married priests in other denominations have not been able accomplish? The church authority should make celibacy optional. According to this paper, Jesus makes celibacy optional in Matthew 19: 11 and 12. Paul in his epistles also make celibacy elective in 1 Corinthians 7:1-9. History also revealed that the primary reason celibacy was enforced was to disallow the priests' families from inheriting the Church properties. Therefore, it is not an attempt to obey the New Testament injunctions that celibacy became an order that must be

strictly observed in Catholic, rather for economic and political reasons. Since mandatory celibacy is not biblical, the Catholic Church is advised to make it optional and married priests should not be denied of any privilege nor limited in their duties as priests.

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